

Supplementary Material

Iodine-Hoechst Enhances X-ray Sensitivity of Cancer Cells Under Normal and Low Oxygen Conditions

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1. Cytotoxicity Assay of Iodine-Hoechst

Cytotoxicity of iodine-Hoechst (IH) was examined by colony formation assay. EMT6 cancer cells were treated with various concentrations of IH. After 24 h of incubation, the cells were collected and seeded on a dish after washing. After 7-day incubation, the cells were stained with Giemsa and colony formation was examined. As shown in Supplementary Figure S1, toxicity of IH was minimum, as increasing concentration of IH had little effect on cell growth.

Figure S1: Survival of EMT6 cancer cells treated with different concentrations of iodine-Hoechst (IH). Values represent mean \pm standard deviation (SD) ($n = 3$).

2. Radiation Enhancement Test of Hoechst without Iodine

To investigate whether the radiation enhancement effect of iodine-Hoechst (IH) was due to iodine, the radiation enhancement of Hoechst 33258, which does not contain iodine, was examined. EMT6 cells were incubated with or without 1 μ M Hoechst 33258 for 24 h on dishes, then collected and suspended in tubes. After X-ray irradiation (2–8 Gy), cells were washed, seeded, and cultured for 7 days, then colony formation was examined. As shown in Supplementary Figure S2, the surviving fraction of cancer cells treated with Hoechst 33258 was comparable to that of the control (No drug).

Figure S2: Radiation enhancement test of Hoechst without iodine by colony formation assay. EMT6 cells were irradiated with conventional X-rays in the presence and absence of Hoechst 33258 under low oxygen condition. Values represent mean \pm standard deviation (SD). ($n = 3$). n.s., not significant.

3. Oxygen Concentration inside AnaeroPouch

To confirm the decrease in oxygen concentration inside AnaeroPouch-Anaero (MITSUBISHI GAS CHEMICAL COMPANY, INC., Tokyo, Japan), oxygen concentration was measured by placing an oxygen concentration meter (GOA-6H, GASTEC CORPORATION, Kanagawa, Japan) inside the pouch. As shown in Supplementary Figure S3, oxygen concentration decreased rapidly, and after 20 min, almost no oxygen remained in the pouch.

Figure S3: Oxygen concentration inside AnaeroPouch. Oxygen concentration was measured with (+) or without (-) an AnaeroPack inside the AnaeroPouch.